

Semantic Metadata Schema for Risks and Mitigations Associated with Outputs from Trusted Research Environments

*Trupti Padiya¹, Jim Smith, Felix Ritchie, Elizabeth Green,
University of the West of England²*

1. Executive Summary

The document proposes a semantically structured metadata schema adhering to W3C standards, to represent risks and mitigations associated with statistical outputs, for the process of statistical disclosure control. The semantic metadata schema (from now referred to as “schema”) is designed to address the following core objectives:

- Provide a modular, scalable design that can adapt to changing needs and be easily integrated into automated processing systems.
- Enable principled comparisons between manual processes and the functionality provided by different versions of automated software.
- Support extensibility and serve as a basis for supporting complex output structures such as AI models.

Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary.....	1
2. Purpose and Scope	2
3. Modelling the Statbarn Taxonomy.....	5
4. Schema for different statbarns.....	7
5. Key Benefits of the Schema.....	20
6. Conclusion.....	20
7. References	21
8. Appendix: Classes and properties in the Semantic Metadata Schema for Statistical Risks and Mitigations.....	21

¹ Corresponding author. Trupti.Padiya@uwe.ac.uk

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2. Purpose and Scope

This document proposes a semantically structured metadata schema adhering to W3C standards, to represent **risks and mitigations** associated with research outputs, for the process of statistical disclosure control. The semantic metadata schema (from now referred to as “schema”) is designed to address the following core objectives:

- Provide a **modular, scalable design** that can adapt to changing needs and be easily integrated into automated processing systems.
- **Enable principled comparisons** between manual processes and the functionality provided by different versions of automated software.
- **Support extensibility and serve as a basis for supporting complex output structures such as AI models.**

To create this schema we build on two complementary developments: the statbarn (Green, Ritchie and White 2024) (Ritchie, et al. 2023), and the Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV) (J. Pandit, et al. 2024) and its Risk Extension (Esteves, Golpayegani, et al., Data Privacy Vocabulary 2025).

We also make an important distinction between (i) conducting risk assessments, and (ii) making disclosure control decisions. This distinction allows us to deliberately side-step two issues:

- The sensitivity of different data sets: Risks may result from a given form of analysis, even if the nature of the data means they have no meaningful impact.
- Rules vs. Principles-based output checking: Regardless of whether a TRE will allow ‘exceptions’, disclosure control decisions should be informed by a thorough risk assessment.

2.1. Background: The Statbarn Framework

The Statbarns taxonomy (Green, Ritchie and White 2024) (Ritchie, et al. 2023)

... is a framework to classify all statistical terms by their disclosure characteristics, including risk, exceptions and mitigation measures. This statbarn massively reduces the dimensionality of the disclosure checking problem, as well as providing improved clarity. It also creates a feasible basis for automatic disclosure control checking (Green et al 2024)

The taxonomy groups different types of analyses into 14 different ‘Statbarns’ according to the nature of the outputs they produce and the various associated disclosure risks. It is consistent with existing best practice as highlighted in, for example, the Secure Data Access Professionals handbook (Griffiths et al 2019). Importantly, it aims to provide a

route for National Statistics Institutes (NSIs), and a wide range of TREs to find consensus on manual practice. However, many NSIs, and increasingly TREs make use of (semi) automated tools as part of their OSDC practice, such as Tau Argus, Table - builder, DataSHIELD or SACRO. The goal of ensuring consistency creates a demand for a set of unambiguous, human-readable and machine actionable statements describing best practice.

2.2. Background: Data Privacy Vocabulary

The schema uses a rich semantic representation to model the Statbarn Taxonomy adhering to the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) standards. It includes core concepts of statbarn (e.g., statistical terms, risks, mitigations) organised as class hierarchies extended from the Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV) (J. Pandit, et al. 2024) and its Risk Extension (Esteves, Golpayegani, et al., Data Privacy Vocabulary 2025). DPV is an established, internationally recognised vocabulary and ontology, which represent concepts about use and processing of data, their associated risks and impacts, and can aid reasoning relevant to data privacy. The DPV Risk extension consists of concepts related to information associated with risks. The schema mainly builds on two key concepts:

- [*dpv:Risk*](#) represents the concept of 'risk' i.e. a possibility or potential of negative events to occur and is indicated using the relation [*dpv:hasRisk*](#).
- [*dpv:RiskMitigationMeasure*](#) represents a method or process or control to mitigate the risk, and is associated using the relation [*dpv:isMitigatedByMeasure*](#)

and these are accompanied by a rich set of relationships, constraints, and attributes such as likelihoods, and measures, facilitating machines to understand and reason about risks and mitigations associated with processes.

The schema serves as a key component for a lightweight ontology using OWL/RDF to enable structured representation and reasoning about privacy-related disclosure risks and mitigation measures without needing overly complex logical structures.

In addition, SHACL will be used to specify some meta-data (e.g. the cardinality of relationships) and validate knowledge-graphs (representing sets of analyses) and enforce rules. For example, we use SHACL to specify that for a given dataset there is exactly one 'minimumThreshold' for the number of respondents in a cell.

Our proposed schema creates a new class *Statbarn*, and leverages existing DPV properties, and SDC-specific extensions of classes/concepts to create a semantic model of OSDC. The conceptual overview is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Conceptual Overview of Risks and Mitigations for OSDC

The major classes/concepts that are extended from DPV and its risk extension are *dpv:Risk*, *dpv:Likelihood*, *dpv:RiskMitigationMeasure*, *risk:RiskEvaluation*, and *risk:Criteria*. Figure 1 shows likelihood with 5 likelihood levels e.g. very high, high, moderate, low and very low. It is possible to add likelihood levels at the scale of 3 e.g. high, moderate, low or at the scale of 7 e.g. extremely high, very high, high, moderate, low, very low, extremely low.

The properties of the DPV Vocabulary reused in this schema are *dpv:hasRisk*, *risk:hasRiskEvaluation*, *dpv:hasLikelihood*, *risk:hasRiskCriteria*, and *dpv:isMitigatedByMeasure*. Class level restrictions are applied to the properties that are reused from DPV, to emphasis their semantic context for the domain of SDC. The schema is easier to understand, integrate, and extend.

3. Modelling the Statbarn Taxonomy

“Statbarn” serves as the base class in the schema. The statbarn framework includes 14 statistical terms, and they are modelled as subclasses of the base class – Statbarn, as shown in Figure 2. Statbarn has following subclasses: 1) Frequencies, 2) StatisticalHypothesisTest, 3) Position, 4) Shape, 5) LinearAggregations, 6) Mode, 7) EndPoints, 8) NonlinearConcentrationRatios, 9) CalculatedRatios, 10) HazardSurvivalTables, 11) GiniCoefficient, 12) LinkedMultilevelTables, 13) Clusters, and 14) CorrelationCoefficients.

Figure 2 Statbarn Hierarchy

3.1. Extending dpv:Risk

The *dpv:Risk* class is extended to represent several types of risks associated with different statbarns. The hierarchy of the risks is depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Types of Risks in SDC

3.2. Extending risk:MitigationControl

The *risk:MitigationControl* → *risk:ProactiveControl* → *risk:RiskControl* → *dpv:RiskMitigationMeasure* is extended to represent risk mitigation measures associated with different risks. Figure 4 shows the hierarchy of risk mitigation measures used for the statbarn. Clearly this is not complete (for example, algorithms for achieving Differential Privacy could be a sub-class of ‘Targeted Noise’). However, as our aim is to provide a unique namespace for this schema, it can simply be extended to encompass more mitigations.

3.3. Extending risk:RiskEvaluation

The *risk:RiskEvaluation* is extended to represent various checks associated with different statbarns as shown in Figure 5. These checks form the basis of risk assessment for output disclosure control. To make the schema generally applicable and to separate *risk:RiskEvaluation* from TRE and dataset-specific choices, they have associated parameters.

Figure 4 Types of Risk Mitigation Measures in SDC

Figure 5 Types of Risk Evaluations in SDC

3.4. Extending risk:RiskCriteria

The *risk:RiskCriteria* is extended to represent various risk criteria - typically numerical or Boolean values - provided by TREs. These are used to parameterise risk checks- for example, the size of the smallest group allowed (Minimum Threshold), or whether Class Disclosure is an issue (RequiredZerocheck) – and may vary between TREs and datasets. They represent vital aspects of the TREs (or their data owners) risk appetite. These are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Risk Criteria from TREs for risk evaluations.

Appendix 1 provides additional details about all the classes and properties defined and used in the schema. The statbarns: Linked multilevel tables and Clusters needs refinement and hence are not represented in this document.

4. Schema for different statbarns

The next sections present visualisations of all the Statbarn schemas, starting with a worked example of how the most common – ‘frequencies’ is created.

4.1. Statbarn: Frequencies

Figure 7 presents the schema for the statbarn “Frequencies” detailing associated risks and mitigations. Figure 8 shows all the subclass hierarchy of Frequencies: AlluvialFlow, CrossTab, FrequencyTable, Histogram, and so on. These subclasses inherit all the risk associations, risk likelihood, and risk mitigation measures.

These figures are graph models representing the schema and provides foundation for a knowledge graph, but this is less amenable to human inspection. We have colour-coded it to make it more human-readable:

- The **statbarn** (type of query) is in yellow
- Potential **risks** are in orange
- **Mitigations** are in green
- Associated with each risk is a check (**purple**) with associated parameters (**blue**).
- The **risk likelihood** (beige) is calculated through of combination of (i) check results, and (ii) whether a mitigation has been applied.

Figure 7 Statbarn: Frequencies

Figure 7 describes that every instance of Frequencies is associated with specific types of privacy risks: LowCounts, Differencing and ClassDisclosure. In turn, each risk represents details about their risk evaluations and mitigations. In this case it can be seen (visually) or inferred (programmatically) that Suppression and Noise are valid mitigations for all three risks.

Diving deeper, LowCount is a risk associated with Frequencies, and must be checked for the minimum threshold and if it fails the check, there is a higher likelihood of risk, and the mitigation measures (e.g. suppression) must be applied. The idea is captured by the semantic model:

- Class LowCount is associated to class MinimumThresholdCheck using *risk:hasRiskEvaluation*.
- MinimumThresholdCheck further links to the class MinimumThreshold, which holds a literal value provided by the TRE.
- The class LowCount is also connected to the *dpv:Likelihood* using *dpv:hasLikelihood* to represent the likelihood of the risk.
- The risk LowCount is mitigated by Noise, Rounding, or Suppression via *dpv:isMitigationMeasure*

The other two risks present are modelled in the same way.

Note that we use the risk criteria *RequiredZeroCheck* to provide a mechanism for TREs to state that class disclosure is not an issue for their data.

The graphical representation of the schema suggests that the risk posed by LowCount in frequencies data can be 1) recognized, 2) assessed, and 3) mitigated via known SDC techniques. Similarly, other risks like ClassDisclosure and Differencing, their likelihood, and their mitigation measures pertaining to the Frequencies statbarn can be interpreted from Figure 7.

Figure 8 Subclass hierarchy for Frequencies

4.2. Statbarn: Position

Figure 9 represents the schema for the statbarn “Position”. Figure 10 shows all the subclass hierarchy of Position: Quartile, Box plot and so on.

Figure 9 Statbarn: Position

Figure 10 Subclass hierarchy for Position

4.3. Statbarn: Shape

Figure 11 represents the schema for the statbarn “Shape”. Figure 12 shows all the subclass hierarchy of Shape: Kurtosis, StandardDeviation, and so on.

Figure 11 Statbarn: Shape

Figure 12 Subclass hierarchy for Shape

4.4. Statbarn: Linear Aggregations

Figure 13 represents the schema for the statbarn “Linear Aggregations”. Figure 14 shows all the subclass hierarchy of Linear Aggregation: Mean, Sum, BarGraph, and so on.

Figure 13 Statbarn: Linear Aggregations

Figure 14 Subclass hierarchy for Linear Aggregation

4.5. Statbarn: Mode

Figure 15 represents the schema for the statbarn “Mode”.

Figure 15 Statbarn: Mode

4.6. Statbarn: End Points

Figure 16 represents the schema for the statbarn “EndPoints”. Figure 17 shows subclasses for EndPoints: Minimum, Maximum, and Range.

Figure 16 Statbarn: End Points

Figure 17 Subclass hierarchy for End Points

4.7. Statbarn: Non-linear Concentration Ratios

Figure 18 represents the schema for the statbarn “NonLinearConcentrationRatios”.

Figure 19 shows NonLinearConcentrationRatios has a subclass

HerfindhalHirschmanIndex.

Figure 18 Statbarn: Non-linear Concentration Ratios

Figure 19 Subclass hierarchy for Non-linear Concentration Ratios

4.8. Statbarn: Calculated Ratios

Figure 20 represents the schema for the statbarn “CalculatedRatios”. Figure 21 shows all the subclasses of CalculatedRatios: CalculatedAnalysis, OddRatios, and RiskRatios.

Figure 20 Statbarn: Calculated Ratios

Figure 21 Subclass hierarchy for Calculated Ratios

4.9. Statbarn: HazardSurvival Tables

Figure 22 represents the schema for the statbarn “Hazard Survival Tables”. Figure 23 shows all the subclasses of HazardSurvivalTables: Kaplan_Miere, HazardTables and SurvivalTables.

Figure 22 Statbarn: Hazard Survival Tables

Figure 23 Subclass hierarchy for Hazard Survival Tables

4.10. Statbarn: Gini Coefficient

Figure 24 represents the schema for the statbarn “Gini Coefficient”. Figure 25 shows GiniCoefficient has a subclass GiniCurves.

Figure 24 Statbarn: Gini Coefficient

Figure 25 Subclass hierarchy for Gini Coefficient

4.11. Statbarn: Correlation Coefficients

Figure 26 represents the schema for the statbarn “Correlation Coefficients”. Table 1 presents diverse types of Correlation Coefficients, each is represented as a subclass of the CorrelationCoefficients class.

Table 1 Types of Corelation Coefficient

ANCOVA	Multinomial logit
Binary Logistic Regression	Multiple regression
Canonical Correlation	Multivariate analysis of variance
Contrast Coefficients	Odds Ratios (estimated)
Correlation Coefficients	Omnibus tests of model coefficients
Covariates	Panel data models
General linear model	Partial correlation coefficients
Kendall’s rank	Phi coefficient
Kernel Estimates	Probit
Linear Regression Coefficients	Standardised regression coefficients
Logistic regression	Structural equation modelling
Logit	Three-stage least squares
Log-linear for higher order tables	Two-stage least squares
Longitudinal estimation	Two-way analysis of variance
MANCOVA	Zero-order correlation

Figure 26 Statbarn: Corelation Coefficients

4.12. Statbarn: Statistical Hypothesis Test

Figure 27 represents the schema for the statbarn “Statistical Hypothesis Test”. Table 2 presents different types of Statistical Hypothesis Tests and each is represented as a subclass of the StatisticalHypothesisTest.

Table 2 Types of Statistical Hypothesis Test

Adjusted R Squared	Eigenvalues – Scree plots	Mauchly's sphericity test
Analysis of variance	Eta Squared	McNemar's test
ANOVA	Friedman test	Nagelkerke R Squared
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Homogeneity of Regression	Paired t-tests
Box's Test of Equality of Covariance Matrices	Homogeneity of Variance	Parallel analysis
Chi-Squared test	Homogeneity of Variance-Covariance matrices	Partial eta squared
Cochran's Q test	Hosmer-Lemeshow test	Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficient
Coefficient of determination	Independent t-tests	Pearson's r
Cohen's d	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin test	Principal component analysis
Cohen's kappa coefficient	Kappa Measure of Agreement	Pseudo-R-squared
Confidence intervals	Kolmogorov-Smirnov test	R Squared
Cox & Snell R Squared	Kruskal-Wallis test	Spearman's rank correlation coefficient
Cramer's V	Lambda	Tukey's honestly significant difference test
Discriminant Function Analysis	Levene's test	Wilcoxon signed rank test
Discriminant Validity	Mann-Whitney U test	Wilks's Lambda

Figure 27 Statbarn: Statistical Hypothesis Tests

5. Key Benefits of the Schema

- Formalise Statistical Outputs, Privacy Risks, and mitigations:**
 The schema provides a structured, machine-readable framework for the statbarn taxonomy that semantically models risks related to statistical outputs and recommends suitable mitigations adhering to W3C standards.
- Facilitates Automated Reasoning:**
 The schema facilitates automated reasoning to determine which risks apply to given statistical outputs because the concepts and relationships are explicitly defined using semantics and connected to standardised vocabularies e.g. the Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV).
- Ensures Conceptual Consistency and Interoperability:**
 The schema extends the DPV framework for the domain of Statistical Disclosure Control, standardised definitions, and promotes interoperability.

6. Conclusion

The schema provides a formal framework for reasoning about statistical outputs in terms of their privacy risks. It can facilitate automated tools to infer which risks apply and guides through applicable risk mitigations. It creates consistency in how statistical disclosure control concepts are described and linked with DPV concepts. This

metadata schema for the statbarn serve as a foundation for statistical disclosure control and can support complex output structures such as AI models.

7. References

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8. Appendix: Classes and properties in the Semantic Metadata Schema for Statistical Risks and Mitigations

Table 3 Classes in the Semantic Metadata Schema for Statistical Risks and Mitigations

Classes	Superclass	Description
Statbarn	Owl:Thing	It is the base class of the taxonomy representing domain-specific concept related to statistical disclosure control classification framework.
LowCount	dpv:Risk	Represents a disclosure risk where attributes can be inferred from the data.

ClassDisclosure	dpv:Risk	Represents disclosure risk where disclosure happens at a class/category level.
Differencing	dpv:Risk	Representing disclosure risk from comparing linked tables to find differences.
LowDOF	dpv:Risk	Represents disclosure risk associated with less variability in data.
Dominance	dpv:Risk	Represents a disclosure risk that arises when a small number of contributors account for a large proportion of a cell's total value.
AuxiliaryInfo	dpv:Risk	Represents a disclosure risk when external or background knowledge can be combined with released data to re-identify individuals or infer confidential attributes.
ImplicitTables	dpv:Risk	Represents a disclosure risk when sensitive information can be inferred indirectly by comparing related tables or sub tables.
Noise	dpv:RiskMitigationMeasure	Represents technique to mitigate disclosure risks that involves adding random variation to data to mask individual values.
Rounding	dpv:RiskMitigationMeasure	Represents technique to mitigate disclosure risks by modifying numerical values (e.g., counts or totals) to the nearest specified base.
Suppression	dpv:RiskMitigationMeasure	Represents technique to mitigate disclosure risks by removing specific data values with high disclosure risk.
Outlier Removal	dpv:RiskMitigationMeasure	Represents technique to mitigate disclosure risks by excluding extreme or unique data points.
Aggregation	dpv:RiskMitigationMeasure	Represents technique to mitigate disclosure risks by combining individual data points into broader categories or groups.
MinimumThresholdCheck	risk:RiskEvaluation	Represents a check required for Minimum threshold.
PresenceOfLinkedTablesCheck	risk:RiskEvaluation	Represents a check required for presence of linked tables.

PrsesenceOfZerosCheck	risk:RiskEvaluation	Represents a check required for presence of zeros.
RequiredZeroCheck	risk:RiskEvaluation	Represents a check required for assessing the risk of class disclosure whether the TRE specifies Presence of Zeros to be checked or not. Some organizations view zero values as a disclosure risk requiring a ZeroCheck, while others do not, so it is important to assess whether a ZeroCheck is required in each context.
PQCheck	risk:RiskEvaluation	Represents a check that evaluates statistical outputs using a PQ Test.
NKCheck	risk:RiskEvaluation	Represents a check that applies the NK Test.
MinimumDOFCheck	risk:RiskEvaluation	Represents a check that evaluates whether the degrees of freedom in statistical outputs meet the predefined MinimumDOF threshold.
StatbarnDataCheck	risk:RiskEvaluation	Represents a check that verifies whether the data displayed in a Statbarn is relevant and appropriate for release.
MinimumThreshold	risk:RiskCriteria	Represents a risk criteria for minimum threshold designed to reduce disclosure risk by setting a minimum count or value that data cells must meet to be published. It is associated with a decimal value.
PresenceOfZero	risk:RiskCriteria	Represents a risk criterion that flags or monitors whether zero values occur in data cells, as the presence of zeros can increase disclosure risk, It is associated with a Boolean value.
PresenceOfLinkedTables	risk:RiskCriteria	Represents a risk criterion that identifies or monitors when multiple related tables or datasets are linked, as such connections can increase disclosure risk. It is associated with a Boolean value.
ZeroCheck	risk:RiskCriteria	Represents a risk criterion from TREs if presence of zero is checked and is associated with a Boolean value.

PRatio	risk:RiskCriteria	Represents a risk criterion that evaluates disclosure risk using a statistical test, where a p-value indicates whether the data meet acceptable thresholds for safe release. It is associated with decimal value.
NValue	risk:RiskCriteria	Represents a risk criterion used in the NK test to represent the minimum number of contributors required in a cell to consider it non-disclosive.
KValue	risk:RiskCriteria	KValue is used in the NK test to specify the maximum allowable contributions.
MinimumDOF	risk:RiskCriteria	Represents a risk criterion that sets the minimum acceptable degrees of freedom for statistical outputs.
StatbarnRelevantShowData	risk:RiskCriteria	Represents a risk criterion that ensures only necessary and relevant data is displayed.
Frequencies	Statbarn	Frequencies is one of the statbarn.
Frequencytable, Histogram, PieChart, ScatterGraph, Heatmap, LineGraph, and so on.	Frequencies	Subclasses of Frequencies.
StatisticalHypothesisTests	Statbarn	Statistical hypothesis tests is one of the statbarn.
Position	Statbarn	Position is one of the statbarn.
Quartile, Box plot and so on.	Position	Subclasses of Position.
Shape	Statbarn	Shape is one of the statbarn.
Kurtosis, StandardDeviation, and so on.	Shape	Subclasses of Shape.
LinearAggregations	Statbarn	Linear Aggregations is one of the statbarn.
Mean, Sum, BarGraph, and so on	Linear Aggregations	Subclasses of LinearAggregations.
Mode	Statbarn	Mode is one of the statbarn.
Clusters	Statbarn	Clusters is one of the statbarn.
EndPoints	Statbarn	End Points is one of the statbarn.
Minimum, Maximum, and Range	EndPoints	Subclasses of EndPoints.
NonLinearConcentrationRatios	Statbarn	Non-linear Concentration Ratios is one of the statbarn.

HerfindhalHirschmanIndex	NonLinearConcentrationRatios	Subclass of NonLinearConcentrationRatios.
CalculatedRatios	Statbarn	Calculated Ratios is one of the statbarn.
CalculatedAnalysis, OddRatios, and RiskRatios	CalculatedRatios	Subclasses of CalculatedRatios.
CorelationCoefficients	Statbarn	Corelation Coefficients is one of the statbarn.
HazardSurvivalTables	Statbarn	Hazard Survival Tables is one of the statbarn.
Kaplan_Miere, HazardTables and SurvivalTables	HazardSurvivalTables	Subclasses of HazardSurvivalTables.
GiniCoefficient	Statbarn	Gini Coefficient is one of the statbarn.
GiniCurves	Ginicoefficient	Subclass of Ginicoefficient.
LinkedMultilevelTables	Statbarn	Linked Multilevel Tables is one of the statbarn.

Table 4 Properties in the Semantic Metadata Schema for Statistical Risks and Mitigations

Property	Type	Description
dpv:hasRisk	Object Property	Links Statbarn to Risks. Class-level restrictions on dpv:hasRisk are applied. For example, the class Frequencies is defined with restrictions on the property dpv:hasRisk such that it must be associated with at least one of these risk classes: ClassDisclosure, Differencing, or LowCount.
risk:hasRiskEvaluation	Object Property	Links Risks to Risk Evaluations to evaluate it. Class-level restrictions on risk:hasRiskEvaluation are applied. For example, the class LowCount is defined with restrictions on the property risk:hasRiskEvaluation such that it must be associated with at least one instance of the class MinimumThresholdCheck.
risk:hasRiskCriteria	Object Property	Links Risk Evaluations to RiskCriteria. Class-level restrictions are applied to specify the type of measure relevant in each risk evaluation. Eg. MinimumThresholdCheck must include a MinimumThreshold.

dpv:isMitigatedbyMeasure	Object Property	Links risks to their mitigation measures. class-level restrictions on dpv:isMitigatedByMeasure are applied. For example, for the risk class LowCount, it has either of the mitigation measures to apply: Suppression, Noise or Rounding
dpv:hasLikelihood	Object Property	Links Risk concept with Likelihood and Risk Evaluation with Likelihood adhering to the semantics of DPV and its risk extension. Necessary class-level restrictions are applied, and it is contextualised without redefining global domain and range.
dpv:hasRiskLevel	Object Property	Links risks to its risk levels. Same as DPV.
hasDecimalValue	Data Property	Used in restrictions to specify fixed types of property values (e.g. thresholds)
hasBooleanValue	Data Property	Used in restrictions to specify fixed types of property values (e.g. PresenceOfZeros)
rdfs:comment	Annotation Property	Provides textual descriptions for classes or entities, e.g. statbarns, risks, and mitigations